

D3.1 EOSC Data Commons architecture, functional specifications no.1

31/12/2025

Abstract

This deliverable presents the initial architecture and functional specifications of the EOSC Data Commons, a federated framework enabling AI-enhanced discovery, access, analysis, and reuse of research data across distributed repositories and compute environments. It outlines the architectural vision, requirements, principles, and decision processes that guide the design of the two core services: the EOSC Matchmaker, which integrates heterogeneous metadata, supports discovery and pairs datasets with analytical tools; and the EOSC Data Player, which orchestrates data access, provisioning, and workflow execution across the compute continuum. The document provides a detailed description of the components, interfaces, and interoperability mechanisms that underpin these services, and establishes the foundation for their first integrated release and future evolution within the EOSC ecosystem.

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Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the initial architecture and functional specifications of the EOSC Data Commons and how it contributes towards building a federated, interoperable, and AI-enabled European Research Commons. The document defines the architectural vision, principles, components, and interactions that enable researchers to discover, access, analyse, and reuse datasets across a distributed landscape of thematic, national, and institutional repositories.

The architecture is centred on two services. The **EOSC Matchmaker** provides an AI-enhanced metadata warehouse and discovery layer that integrates heterogeneous repository metadata, supports natural language searches, performs FAIRness assessments, and pairs datasets with suitable analytical tools. It delivers these capabilities through a set of modular components. It also generates a *Package for Processing Datasets* as an interoperable format for enabling data re-use in EOSC.

Complementing this, the **EOSC Data Player** enables the deployment and execution of analyses across the compute continuum—from interactive notebook environments to HPC, HTC, and cloud platforms. It orchestrates the preparation of computational environments, manages data access via a unified layer, and executes workflows through a pluggable set of compute engines. Together, these services provide a coherent mechanism for a seamless transition from discovery to analysis, while ensuring reproducibility, traceability, and alignment with EOSC Core capabilities.

The deliverable also captures the architectural requirements derived from early use cases, documents the methodology for requirement refinement, and summarises the architecture decision records that guide key design choices. It situates the services within the EOSC Interoperability Framework, ensuring compatibility with EOSC Nodes, AAI, accounting, monitoring, and resource catalogues.

This initial architecture forms the basis for the first release of the EOSC Data Commons services and provides a forward-looking foundation for future iterations. Feedback from pilot deployments, evolving EOSC Federation developments, and the refinement of use-case requirements will inform the next architectural update in D3.3. The work presented here lays the groundwork for a scalable, extensible, and interoperable ecosystem enabling researchers to conduct FAIR, reproducible, and cross-disciplinary data-intensive science across Europe.

1. Introduction

The EOSC Data Commons project advances the vision of a federated European Research Commons by enabling seamless discovery, access, analysis, sharing, and reuse of research data across the compute continuum. As research increasingly depends on distributed and heterogeneous data resources and diverse computing environments, there is a growing need for integrated services that can connect datasets, tools, and execution platforms in a coherent, interoperable manner. EOSC Data Commons addresses this need by delivering a unified architecture that supports the full data lifecycle—from initial discovery of datasets, to selection and pairing of analytical tools, to the automated deployment and execution of workflows.

This deliverable describes the first functional architecture of the EOSC Data Commons, developed within the project Work Package 3. The architecture is built from the principles of federation, modularity, interoperability, and extensibility, ensuring that services can evolve alongside the broader EOSC ecosystem and adapt to emerging scientific and technical requirements. Two flagship services form the core of the architecture: the EOSC Matchmaker (originally named AI-based Analytics Oriented Metadata Warehouse and Discovery Service, AI-MWDS), providing AI-enhanced metadata integration, discovery, FAIRness assessment, and deterministic/semantic pairing of datasets with tools; and the EOSC Data Player (originally named Data Analysis Orchestration and Deployment Service - DAODS), orchestrating data access, environment provisioning, and execution of analyses on diverse compute platforms.

The document introduces the architectural framework, outlines key requirements gathered from cross-disciplinary use cases, explains the rationale behind major architectural decisions, and describes the internal components and interfaces of both core services. It also situates the architecture within the EOSC Interoperability Framework and highlights its alignment with EOSC Core services, policies, and operational models. Together, these elements establish a coherent foundation for implementing the first release of the EOSC Data Commons services and for supporting future iterations of the system.

1.1. Scope and Purpose of the document

The purpose of this document is to present the initial functional and logical architecture of the EOSC Data Commons and to provide a coherent framework for the design, integration, and future evolution of its core services. It defines the architectural vision and principles guiding the development of the EOSC Matchmaker and EOSC Data Player, and describes how these services enable interoperable discovery, pairing, packaging, and execution of data-driven analyses across the compute continuum.

1.2. Structure of the document

The document is organised into the following main sections:

- Architecture Framework – Describes the architectural vision, requirements, guiding principles, and decision-making mechanisms (ADRs) underlying the EOSC Data Commons design.
- Context – Outlines the system boundaries and assumptions shaping the architecture.
- EOSC Matchmaker – Introduces the AI-enabled discovery and metadata integration service, detailing its internal components, ingestion workflows, search capabilities, FAIRness assessment, and the generation of the Package for Processing Datasets.
- EOSC Data Player – Describes the orchestration and execution service, including its dispatcher, data access layer, deployment tools, and compute engine plugins enabling analysis execution across diverse platforms.
- EOSC Interoperability – Illustrates how the services integrate with EOSC Core capabilities.
- Conclusions and Future Work – Summarises the main outcomes and outlines the planned evolution of the architecture towards future service releases and updates.

2. Architecture Framework

The Architecture Framework defines the core structure and guiding principles of the EOSC Data Commons. It outlines how requirements from project use cases shape the system design and ensures that all components are developed in a coherent, interoperable, and scalable manner. This section summarises the requirement collection process, presents the architectural principles guiding the system's design, and introduces the use of Architecture Decision Records (ADRs) as a lightweight method for documenting key technical choices.

2.1. Requirements overview

The EOSC Data Commons architecture is driven by the requirements stemming from the use cases of the project. These requirements are described in depth in [D4.1 Requirement analysis and specification](#), [D5.1 Landscape analysis for the packaging specification and components](#) and [D7.1 Initial Use Cases Analysis and Requirements Report](#), focusing on the design of the Metadata Warehouse as a central metadata repository and associated index ([D4.1](#)); a review of the design considerations, standards, specifications, and important implementations that apply to File Type and Tool Registries ([D5.1](#)); and the requirements stemming from the initial use cases analysis ([D7.1](#)). This section summarises the requirements-gathering process and the initial requirements that have guided the initial architecture design for the services.

The requirement collection methodology was defined in cooperation with WP7 (devoted to the use cases support) and WP3 (focused on the architecture), starting with the following steps:

- Creation of a components inventory collecting the planned service components at the beginning of the project, with clear descriptions for use cases to understand how the components can be leveraged in their use cases
- Definition of initial high-level requirements from use cases after analysis of the components.
- Establishment of work groups complementing the existing work package structure to speed up cross-work package collaborations and focus on further evolution and refinement of requirements.

These initial steps kick-started a methodology that iteratively refines the requirements and updates the service components to match the users' needs. The initial iteration has defined the Proof of Concept release, available from Month 8 (November 2025) at <https://dev.matchmaker.eosc-data-commons.eu/>. Subsequent iterations will progressively revise and extend the requirements, and the service architecture will be updated accordingly.

The initial list of high-level requirements for EOSC Data Commons is defined below:

1. Query available datasets in the EOSC Matchmaker.
2. Query available tools in the EOSC Matchmaker.
3. Select a dataset in the EOSC Matchmaker and access it.
4. Select a tool in the EOSC Matchmaker and make it available for analysis.

5. Pair a dataset with tool(s) in a Package for Processing Datasets.
6. Create an interactive user environment for data analytics from a Package for Processing Datasets.
7. Assess the FAIRness of a dataset using the EOSC Matchmaker.

This list led to the creation of six work groups:

- Group 1: Make my data available in the EOSC Matchmaker. For the Proof of Concept release, the group focused on those repositories that support the OAI-PMH protocol.
- Group 2: Make my VRE/tool/workflow available in the EOSC Matchmaker. The group aimed for (deterministic) explicit matchmaking of datasets and tools for the Proof of Concept release.
- Group 3: Integrate my VRE with the EOSC Matchmaker, with no direct activities for the Proof of Concept.
- Group 4: Integrate my VRE with the EOSC Data Player, with no direct activities for the Proof of Concept.
- Group 5: Packages for processing datasets. The group started with JupyterHub/BinderHub, Galaxy, and Infrastructure Manager as main components for the Proof of Concept release, leaving other target environments for upcoming releases.
- Group 6: FAIRness assessment. So far, the group has focused on delivering FAIR testing for published objects with a PID that are available via the API.

For a complete description of the requirements, refer to [DZ.1](#).

2.2. Architecture Principles

EOSC Data Commons is designed following six architectural principles that ensure the system is robust, interoperable, future-proof, and aligned with the broader EOSC vision. The principles are described below:

Federation: EOSC Data Commons services operate in a federated environment where repositories, compute resources and EOSC nodes are autonomous entities that are brought together by following well-defined interfaces, standards and rules. The EOSC Data Commons services enable interoperability among these systems by minimising the imposition of additional requirements.

Modularity: EOSC Data Commons service components should operate in a modular way, allowing the replacement or addition of components without affecting the rest of the system. Components operate independently but integrate via well-defined interfaces.

Extensibility: As the EOSC ecosystem continues to evolve, the EOSC Data Commons services should provide clear extension capabilities via a plugin-based architecture for repositories, compute engines, and data access services. This will provide a future-proof architecture that can adapt to the changing EOSC landscape and also support an incremental development of the system, which brings new integrations as needed by use cases.

Scalability: Services should support increasing data volumes, tools, and compute capacity without affecting performance. Both vertical scaling and horizontal scaling should be possible.

Interoperability: EOSC Data Commons services should follow the relevant EOSC Interoperability Framework and specifically should target interoperability with the EOSC EU Node, ensuring EOSC Data Commons does not operate as a standalone system but as a core part of the federated EOSC ecosystem.

Security and trust: EOSC Data Commons services operate in a federated, cross-border, multi-stakeholder environment where potentially sensitive data and distributed compute resources must interoperate safely and reliably. EOSC Data Commons users should ensure compliant access control, safe workflow execution, integrity of data and provenance, and protection against misuse.

2.3. Architecture Decision Records

Architecture Decision Records (ADRs) provide a lightweight, systematic method for capturing and communicating key architectural decisions throughout the development of the EOSC Data Commons. Given the complexity and distributed nature of the project—spanning the whole data lifecycle—ADRs offer a structured way to ensure transparency, alignment, and long-term maintainability across all participating partners, especially whenever there is a need to take an architecture decision that affects several of the components of the project or those affecting interoperability and the scalability of the project.

ADRs ensure that each important decision:

- Is captured with its context, options, rationale, and consequences
- Remains discoverable for new developers and integrators
- Supports traceability across work packages and releases
- Helps maintain architectural coherence as the system evolves
- Aids onboarding and knowledge transfer across distributed teams and organisations

Any member of the project can trigger the creation of a new ADR whenever a new design question, alternative, or technical challenge emerges. The ADR proposer drafts the document following a template where the following points are captured:

- Proposer: person raising the need for the ADR.
- Status: DRAFT - ADR is in draft state/proposed; ACCEPTED - ADR is agreed; DEPRECATED - ADR is not valid any more; REJECTED - ADR was rejected.
- Date: date of the last status change (e.g. when the ADR was approved).
- Context and Problem Statement: describe the context and problem statement, e.g., in free form using two to three sentences. You may want to articulate the problem in the form of a question.
- Decision: chosen option: "[option 1]", because [justification. e.g., only option, which meets k.o. criterion decision driver | which resolves force force | ... | comes out best].

- Consequences: explains the results of the decision over the long term. Did it work, not work, was changed, upgraded, etc.
- Discussion: explains the forces at play (technical, political, social, project). This is the story explaining the problem we are looking to resolve.
- Links: list of relevant links to the ADR.

Once the ADR is created, the Technical Coordination Board (TCB) of the project reviews it and discusses, ensuring consistency and clarity. Once reviewed, TCB approves the ADR and updates its status and approval date. All ADRs are available in the project's Confluence for reference. [Table 1](#) summarises the ADRs until December 2025.

ADR	Status	Decision
Metadata Warehouse System Design	ACCEPTED 2025-08-12	The Metadata Warehouse hosts the metadata of the available datasets in the EOSC Matchmaker. These datasets are harvested from a number of repositories (target +20 at the end of the project) with potential different metadata schemas. This ADR describes the technical decisions for the design of this system.
Use of RO-Crate for the Package for processing datasets	ACCEPTED 2025-09-24	We need to decide what standards/data formats will be used to express the Request Package - one that is generated at the Matchmaker linking tools and data and sent to the Data Player to run an execution. DataPlayer will accept as input RO-Crate packages, potentially using a hybrid RO-Crate+BagIt approach where BagIt information is wrapped as part of the RO-Crate. Authentication details should NOT be included in the RO-Crate packages to make them re-usable
Choice of an LLM provider	ACCEPTED 2025-10-08	The AI search component will use a Large Language Model (LLM) to enable advanced search of datasets and tools in natural language. We need to decide: Which LLMs to use, and what criteria will guide model selection. Where inference will be computed: self-hosted, or using external providers. The decision should balance cost, performance, scalability, and ease of integration, while ensuring the chosen models support tool calling and European languages.

Table 1 - Summary of ADRs for EOSC Data Commons

Some ADRs may be superseded as the architecture evolves. Those deprecated ADRs remain archived for historical context.

3. Context

EOSC Data Commons aims at integrating data from multiple thematic and national repositories into a unified AI-powered discovery layer, enriched with analytics information and automated workflow execution across the compute continuum. The project should support the full data lifecycle: planning, processing, preservation, sharing, and reuse.

The high-level context architecture of the EOSC Data Commons is shown in [Figure 1](#).

Figure 1 - Context diagram for the EOSC Data Commons Services

EOSC Researchers interact with the EOSC Data Commons services through a web-based User Interface of the EOSC Matchmaker (see [Figure 2](#) for a current Proof of Concept UI screenshot) to discover datasets relevant to their needs, find tools that match those datasets and request the deployment of the tools on an execution platform or VRE. Similarly, external VREs may rely on the EOSC Data Commons services to perform discovery and to deploy analysis tools along these datasets through well-defined APIs. The EOSC Data Commons Services include two main components: (i) the EOSC Matchmaker (metadata

harvesting, AI-based discovery, tool pairing) and (ii) the EOSC Data Player (execution orchestration, workflow deployment).

Data Repositories and Tools repositories are harvested by EOSC Matchmaker to populate the Metadata Warehouse and Tools Catalogue respectively. Execution platforms/VRE represents the compute continuum endpoints where packaged analyses are deployed. This may include: Cloud (e.g. OpenStack) or Kubernetes clusters, HPC/HTC systems, Galaxy instances, JupyterHub environments, Container platforms within the EOSC EU Node and Community-specific execution infrastructures. Data and Tool Repositories may present different interfaces for querying the available entries and the metadata schema of every entry may differ as well for every repository. AI search features rely on external LLM inference servers. The EOSC Matchmaker should be able to harvest different combinations of query interfaces and metadata schemas for both repository types. Likewise, the EOSC Data Player needs to support a wide range of potential execution platforms.

Figure 2 - Proof of Concept User Interface for the EOSC Matchmaker

The EOSC Matchmaker identifies and pairs suitable analytics tools with relevant datasets, producing these combinations as a Package that can be consumed by the EOSC Data Player or other compatible clients that follow the specification. The EOSC Data Player is not expected to deliver a dedicated UI for end-users, but instead, offer an API that can be called from the EOSC Matchmaker UI or from external VREs/systems that offer custom UIs for their users.

Each component of the EOSC Data Commons services will offer well-defined APIs to ensure interoperability, modularity, and seamless integration across them and external components. These APIs expose the capabilities of both core services—the EOSC Matchmaker and the EOSC Data Player—and enable external systems to consume, extend, or integrate their functionalities.

4. EOSC Matchmaker

The EOSC Matchmaker is the AI-based Analytics-Oriented Metadata Warehouse and Discovery service of EOSC Data Commons. It enables:

- Integration of metadata from multiple repositories.
- Discovery of datasets and tools.
- FAIRness assessment.
- Pairing of datasets and software.
- Creation of the Package for Processing Datasets.

For a detailed description of the Matchmaker, associated requirements and design considerations, refer to D4.1 and D5.1 deliverables.

4.1. EOSC Matchmaker Components

Figure 3 shows the component-level architecture of the EOSC Matchmaker, showing how its internal components interact with each other, with the EOSC Researcher, and with external systems such as data repositories, tool repositories, VREs, LLM inference servers and the EOSC Data Player.

The researcher interacts with the system through the User Interface, where they perform searches for datasets; request matching tools for selected datasets; and request analysis deployments. The UI acts as the entry point for all user-driven interactions.

The metadata ingestion and processing pipeline is supported by several components:

- The Metadata Warehouse stores information about the datasets discoverable by the service and indexes that information for its retrieval. A set of Crawlers harvest metadata from the available data repositories via APIs and follow their metadata schemas. The crawlers populate the Metadata Warehouse DB with this information. This operation is performed at regular intervals to ingest new metadata as it is available on the origin repositories.
- The FAIR Assessment toolkit relies on existing FAIR evaluation tools (like [F-UJI](#) and [FAIRCORE4EOSC - CAT: Compliance Assessment Toolkit](#)) to determine the level of FAIRness of datasets, whether they are already available in the source repositories or before their deposit when originated from the services implemented by the project.
- The File Metadata Harvester retrieves file-level metadata on the basis of a PID, and it queries the origin repositories to extract this information. The Type Registry complements the file metadata with detailed file type information from a registry of types.

The Metadata Warehouse is queried by the Data Commons Search service that returns relevant datasets from user queries by relying on an LLM Inference Server to support AI-powered searches. This component can be used from external sources, such as VREs that want to enhance their data discovery capabilities.

Figure 3 - EOSC Matchmaker component diagram

A Tools Registry matches datasets (or data types of specific files within a dataset) with one or more tools that can accommodate such a type as an input, and recommends platforms on which such a tool and corresponding dataset can be deployed. The Tools Registry builds its internal tool catalogue by harvesting external Tool Repositories. A list of potential Tool

Repositories to harvest is available in deliverable [D5.1](#), for the initial stages of the project, the project will focus on [Galaxy ToolShed](#), [RoHub](#), and [WorkflowHub](#).

The Request Packager provides the link between EOSC Data Commons services. It creates the Package, a “virtual bag” of metadata and resource references, carrying all information that is needed for execution. This package gets forwarded to the EOSC Data Player upon user request for execution on the infrastructure.

The following tables provide additional details on the EOSC Matchmaker components.

Component	Metadata Warehouse
TRL	4
Description	Core storage and indexing infrastructure consisting of a database for structured metadata storage and a search engine enabling fast query processing. This component stores harmonised metadata from the crawlers and provides the foundation for discovery services.
Documentation	TBD, under development
API	REST API for triggering the harvesting of repositories implemented in FastAPI (see code repository for details)
Code Repository	https://github.com/EOSC-Data-Commons/metadata-warehouse/ ¹
License	TBD

Table 2 - Metadata Warehouse

Component	Metadata crawlers
TRL	4
Description	<p>Harvesting infrastructure supporting the diverse protocols from the source repositories.</p> <p>It includes sector- and/or technology-specific metadata crawlers that interact with repository interfaces. In particular, crawlers for a series of commonly used technologies for repositories (Dataverse, InvenioRDM, OAI-PMH, etc.) will be co-created in collaboration with the providers of the data repositories, enabling the integration of existing repositories out of the box.</p> <p>Metadata crawlers may enrich the Warehouse with additional information on the datasets. Currently, as this component is in an early design phase, the exact metadata to be enriched is not defined and will be refined with the use cases input as the project further develops.</p>
Documentation	TBD, under development

¹ Link is currently available only for EOSC Data Commons members.

Component	Metadata crawlers
API	No external API available, this component interacts with the origin repositories APIs and populates the Metadata warehouse accordingly.
Code Repository	https://github.com/EOSC-Data-Commons/metadata-crawlers
License	TBD

Table 3 - Metadata crawlers

Component	File Metadata Harvester
TRL	4
Description	<p>The File Metadata Service assists with the retrieval of file-level metadata on the basis of a PID. This process is not standardised for different repository platforms, and the File Metadata Service implements business logic for each repository platform to provide a standardised API for such retrieval, based on a PID.</p> <p>These invocation of the File Metadata Harvested can be triggered on the initial ingestion of metadata by the harvester or on specific events stemming from the interaction with the Matchmaker (e.g. the user selects a specific dataset for analysis).</p> <p>The File Metadata Service can be used to build an inventory of file-level metadata, and provides such metadata on request from the harvest database it maintains in the background.</p>
Documentation	https://github.com/Dans-labs/filemetrix/blob/main/README.md
API	https://filemetrix.labs.dansdemo.nl/docs
Code Repository	https://github.com/Dans-labs/filemetrix
License	MIT

Table 4 - File Metadata Harvester

Component	Data Commons Search
TRL	4
Description	<p>AI-based data discovery service offering two different types of search:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (i) a Basic Search that reuses existing Open Source tools and enables a keyword-based search to obtain datasets and tools related to the user's input keywords, including matching tools for exploring or analysing a given dataset of interest and • (ii) an Advanced Search, leveraging the Knowledge Graph representation of the Metadata Warehouse to deliver a semantic search system leveraging a Large Language Model (LLM) to translate natural language questions into a structured query language (i.e., SPARQL) over the

Component	Data Commons Search
	<p>knowledge graph.</p> <p>The AI-based interaction is designed to communicate with several LLM providers, enabling it to easily switch between different LLM providers and not be tied to a specific one.</p>
Documentation	https://github.com/EOSC-Data-Commons/data-commons-search/blob/main/README.md
API	Supports the Model Context Protocol (MCP) to help users discover datasets and tools via a Large Language Model–assisted search. See the code repository for additional documentation.
Code Repository	https://github.com/EOSC-Data-Commons/data-commons-search
License	MIT

Table 5 - Data Commons Search

Component	Tools Registry
TRL	4
Description	<p>The Tools Registry provides two main functionalities of the Matchmaker:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collect information about available tools from several possible repositories and registries, providing mechanisms for harmonisation and disambiguation of this information, and extend the properties for tools with additional information not provided by the sources, but nevertheless required, for example, to match tools to platforms for execution or successful deployment of code. • Match a data type with one or more tools that can accommodate such a type as an input, and recommend platforms on which such a tool and corresponding dataset can be deployed.
Documentation	https://github.com/Dans-labs/tool-registry/blob/main/README.md
API	https://tool-registry.labs.dansdemo.nl/docs
Code Repository	https://github.com/Dans-labs/tool-registry
License	MIT

Table 6 - Tools Registry

Component	File Type Registry
TRL	4
Description	<p>The Type Registry provides file-type-related services from detailed file characterisation information from a registry of types.</p> <p>The registry of types is a facade registry that combines</p>

Component	File Type Registry
	<p>information from a number of contributing ‘feeder’ registries, combining file type characteristics from all of these. In addition, it needs to analyse feeder registry data to determine possible relationships between types, and assist with the manual curation (annotation) of file type information. To support these harvesting and harmonisation actions, a number of helper services will be required.</p> <p>The Type Registry Service is mainly used by the EOSC Data Commons through a service that characterises a file based on a file extension or a MIME Type. The response to this call is a set of file type properties that can be used to index datasets on the basis of file type characteristics in the Metadata Warehouse.</p>
Documentation	TBD
API	https://type-registry.labs.dansdemo.nl/docs
Code Repository	https://github.com/Dans-labs/type-registry
License	MIT

Table 7 - File Type Registry

Component	Request Packager
TRL	2 ²
Description	<p>The Request Packager provides the basis for reusability and reproducibility of results thanks to its central concept – the Request Package, a “virtual bag” of metadata and resource references, carrying all information that is needed for execution.</p> <p>The Request Packager contains selections by end users of the file(s), tool(s), and execution platform(s) selected for deployment, and packages all of these in a structure that wraps file-level metadata using the BagIt specification in an RO-Crate package that serves as a starting point for provenance recording.</p>
Documentation	TBD
API	TBD, under development.
Code Repository	https://github.com/EOSC-Data-Commons/RequestPackager
License	TBD

Table 8 - Request Packager

Component	FAIR Assessment Toolkit
TRL	4
Description	Integrates FAIR assessment Infrastructure & Tools with the

² The Request Packager is not part of the Proof of Concept demonstrator and therefore has a lower TRL as being in the early prototyping phase.

Component	FAIR Assessment Toolkit
	<p>Metadata Warehouse. Utilises FAIR evaluation to index, filter, and select datasets if needed by the end user to determine FAIRness of datasets.</p> <p>The Compliance Assessment Toolkit (CAT), developed by FAIRCORE4EOSC and earmarked for operational deployment in the EUDAT Node, can be used as an executor, aggregator and registry of test and appraisal outcomes, as well as a knowledge base for FAIR-related guidance and best practices. It provides a conceptual model for the encoding of assessments and can extend FAIR with additional criteria, metrics, benchmarks, and tests.</p>
Documentation	https://fc4e-cat.github.io/fc4e-cat-doc/docs/intro/
API	https://fc4e-cat.github.io/fc4e-cat-doc/openapi/explore
Code Repository	https://github.com/fc4e-cat
License	Apache-2

Table 9 - FAIR Assessment Toolkit

4.2. Runtime view

Figure 4 depicts the main interaction flow of the EOSC Matchmaker components when a user wants to reuse some dataset for a new analysis:

1. Users interact with the EOSC Matchmaker UI to perform searches through Natural Language queries.
2. The UI forwards these queries to the EOSC Data Commons Search, which will, in turn, perform an inference query to a LLM model that returns the search results and are shown back to the user.
3. The user selects a dataset from the list of results and requests from the UI the list of matching tools that can be used for analytics. The UI relies on file metadata to the File Registry and, with that information, requests matching tools to the Type Registry, which is shown to the user.
4. The User can request the deployment of a given tool on the infrastructure to the UI.
5. The UI gets a *Package for Processing Datasets* from the Request Packager and sends this to the EOSC Data Player for its analysis.
6. The EOSC Data Player returns a deployment ID that is used to retrieve the request status; once the request completes, it returns a URL for the user to interact with the analysis tool. Batch analysis returns a URL to retrieve the execution results.

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Figure 4 - EOSC Matchmaker runtime flow

While the diagram shows the flow initiated by an End User interacting with the User Interface, all APIs will be made available for direct interaction from any other third party clients or VREs.

5. EOSC Data Player

The EOSC Data Player is the Data Analysis Orchestration and Deployment service. It interacts with the most appropriate services and infrastructures to process reference data according to the information encoded in the Package for Processing Datasets provided as input to the service.

D6.1 Report on initial use cases deployment and dispatcher prototype (to be delivered in February 2026) will provide an extended description of the EOSC Data Player, associated requirements and design considerations.

5.1. EOSC Data Player Components

Figure 5 shows the component-level architecture of the EOSC Data Player, showing how its internal components interact with each other, with the EOSC Matchmaker, and with external computing platforms where analytics are deployed.

The EOSC Matchmaker is the main client for the Data Player. It sends a Request Dispatch, containing the *Package for Processing Datasets*, to the EOSC Data Player. This package includes:

- references to the selected dataset(s), and
- the selected tool or workflow, including details on the compute requirements and execution platform needed for it.

The EOSC Data Player begins its processing with the Dispatcher component. This is the central orchestrator of the EOSC Data Player. It performs: (i) validation of incoming requests; (ii) triggering deployment tasks whenever needed; (iii) submission of workloads to compute engines; and (iv) coordination of data-access preparation.

The Data Access Tools ensure that data described in the package is available at the execution environment. They resolve references to external data sources, provide mechanisms for staging data onto the compute platform or target VRE, ensuring proper access permissions and identity propagation. The Compute Engines are plugin-based components that submit workloads to various execution environments supported by the EOSC Data Commons. The Compute Engines request from the Deployment Tools the provisioning and deployment of computational environments, e.g. whenever a Virtual Research Environment (VRE) needs to be instantiated or configured on-demand for supporting the execution of the user workload.

The following tables provide additional details on the EOSC Data Player components.

Component	Dispatcher
TRL	4
Description	Entrypoint to the Data Player service. It receives “Packages for Processing Datasets” in the form of RO-Crate and routes tasks to the rest of the components of the service.
Documentation	TBD, in preparation
API	TBD, in preparation
Code Repository	https://github.com/EOSC-Data-Commons/Dispatcher
License	TBD, component in early design phase

Table 10 - Dispatcher

Component	Data Access Layer
TRL	4
Description	<p>A unified layer that organises data access to public and private data repositories. It's integrated with the VREs and Computing Platforms, providing coherent APIs to access the data for computation/analysis:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • extensible/pluggable architecture, bringing together different technologies for data access, • as a baseline solution, includes a lightweight file system-based library (FUSE/PyFilesystem) to expose data as an RO-Crate, so datasets can be easily packaged and used by engines to make them available to users, • can access a dataset based on the information carried by the Request Package, • resolves references across both public and private data, <p>The component developers are currently evaluating different implementation strategies: as a standalone component, part of the Dispatcher, or a set of plugins/libraries/adaptors for individual engines. For the Proof of Concept release a first realisation of the Data Access Layer is delivered using Onedata technology.</p>
Documentation	TBD, in preparation
API	TBD, in preparation
Code Repository	TBD, in preparation. Code repositories for Onedata, available at https://github.com/onedata
License	TBD, component in early design phase

Table 11 - Data Access Layer

Component	Deployment Tools
TRL	9
Description	<p>The Deployment Tools component is based on the Infrastructure Manager (IM), an open-source tool that deploys complex and customised virtual infrastructures on IaaS Cloud deployments (such as AWS, OpenStack, etc.).</p> <p>IM improves access to and usability of IaaS clouds by automating VMI (Virtual Machine Image) selection, deployment, configuration, software installation, monitoring, and updates for the virtual infrastructure. It supports APIs from a large number of virtual platforms, making user applications cloud-agnostic. In addition, it integrates a contextualisation system to enable the installation and configuration of all the user-required applications providing the user with a fully functional infrastructure.</p> <p>The Deployment Tools deploy on available compute platforms the VREs or platforms where the requested analytics can be executed, e.g. it can deploy a Galaxy instance on an OpenStack IaaS cloud to support the execution of a Galaxy workflow.</p>
Documentation	http://imdocs.readthedocs.io/
API	https://imdocs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/REST.html
Code Repository	https://github.com/grycap/im
License	GPL v3.0

Table 12 - Deployment Tools

Component	Compute Engine
TRL	4
Description	<p>Through a plugin-based design, the Compute Engine delivers the mechanisms to instantiate the user workload defined in the Package for Processing Datasets at a compute platform endpoint.</p> <p>Each compute engine accepts as input the package RO-Crate and prepares the target endpoint to execute the workload. Plugins support two modes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • interactive: The target environment for the workflow execution is set up; input data are made available there (uploaded or referenced), and a link to the environment is passed to the user who is expected to start the workflow on their own. • batch: The execution of the workflow in the target environment is triggered by the plugin, and the user is presented with final results. <p>The list of plugins defined at this stage are listed in the following section.</p>

Component	Compute Engine
Documentation	TBD, in preparation
API	No public API, the compute engines are implemented by extending a base class.
Code Repository	https://github.com/EOSC-Data-Commons/Dispatcher
License	TBD, component in early design phase

Table 13 - Compute Engines

5.1.1. Compute Engine plugins

This section lists the foreseen target environments for the Compute Engine plugins at the current development phase of the project. This list will be further refined in D6.1 and the subsequent version of this document (D3.3, due in March 2027).

Platform	Galaxy
TRL	9
Description	<p>Galaxy is an open-source platform that allows researchers to analyse and share scientific data using interoperable APIs and various user-friendly web-based interfaces. The Galaxy project was launched in 2005 and has since become a powerful framework for researchers across a wide range of research fields, including *omics, biodiversity, machine learning, cheminformatics, NLP, material science, climate research, and humanities.</p> <p>Galaxy is a multi-user environment which facilitates sharing of e.g. tools, workflows, notebooks, visualisations, and data with others. Galaxy platform focuses on transparency, reproducibility, and reusability.</p> <p>The Galaxy platform powers the EU Galaxy Server.</p>
Documentation	https://docs.galaxyproject.org/en/master/
API	https://usegalaxy.eu/api/docs
Code Repository	https://github.com/galaxyproject/galaxy
License	MIT

Table 14 - Galaxy

Platform	interLink
TRL	7
Description	interLink is an abstraction layer for the execution of any Kubernetes pod on any remote resource capable of managing a Container execution lifecycle.

Platform	interLink
	<p>It facilitates the development of provider-specific plugins for the Kubernetes Virtual Kubelet interface, so the resource providers can leverage the power of virtual kubelet without a black belt in Kubernetes internals.</p> <p>interLink is hosted by the Cloud Native Computing Foundation (CNCF).</p>
Documentation	https://interlink-hq.github.io/interLink/docs/intro
API	https://interlink-hq.github.io/interLink/docs/guides/api-reference
Code Repository	https://github.com/interlink-hq/interLink
License	Apache-2

Table 15 - interLink

Platform	OSCAR
TRL	7
Description	<p>OSCAR is an open-source platform to support the event-driven serverless computing model for data-processing applications. It can be automatically deployed on multi-Clouds, and even on low-powered devices, to create highly-parallel event-driven data-processing serverless applications across the computing continuum. These applications execute in customised runtime environments provided by Docker containers that run on elastic Kubernetes clusters.</p>
Documentation	https://docs.oscar.grycap.net/
API	https://docs.oscar.grycap.net/api/
Code Repository	http://github.com/grycap/oscar
License	Apache-2

Table 16 - OSCAR

Platform	BinderHub
TRL	9
Description	<p>BinderHub is a Kubernetes-based cloud service that allows users to share reproducible interactive computing environments from code repositories. It is the primary technology behind mybinder.org and EGI Replay service.</p> <p>BinderHub allows users to build and register a Docker image from a Git repository, then connect with JupyterHub, allowing you to</p>

Platform	BinderHub
	create a public IP address that allows users to interact with the code and environment within a live JupyterHub instance. Users can select a specific branch name, commit, or tag to serve.
Documentation	https://binderhub.readthedocs.io/en/latest/
API	https://binderhub.readthedocs.io/en/latest/api.html
Code Repository	https://github.com/jupyterhub/binderhub
License	BSD-3-Clause

Table 17 - BinderHub

Platform	JupyterHub
TRL	9
Description	JupyterHub brings the power of notebooks to groups of users. It gives users access to computational environments and resources without burdening users with installation and maintenance tasks. Users can get their work done in their own workspaces on shared resources, which can be managed efficiently by system administrators. It is the primary technology behind EGI Notebooks and the EOSC EU Node Interactive Notebooks services.
Documentation	https://jupyterhub.readthedocs.io/en/stable/
API	https://jupyterhub.readthedocs.io/en/stable/reference/rest-api.html
Code Repository	https://github.com/jupyterhub/jupyterhub
License	BSD-3-Clause

Table 18 - JupyterHub

Platform	ScienceMesh
TRL	7
Description	Federable sync and share node with access to applications and processing resources (e.g. notebooks and batch capacity). ScienceMesh relies on the Reva project that aims to make cloud storage and application providers interoperable through a common platform. Within EOSC Data Commons, it will be used to interface HPC systems and to demonstrate federated, inter-institutional workflows.
Documentation	https://github.com/cs3org/reva/tree/master/docs , https://cernbox.docs.cern.ch/
API	https://github.com/cs3org/OCM-API
Code Repository	https://github.com/cs3org/reva/
License	Apache-2

5.2. Runtime view

Figure 6 shows the runtime flow for running an analysis requested by the EOSC Matchmaker using a Package for Processing Datasets, where the Compute Engine needs to request the deployment of a VRE for the actual execution of the analysis. A simpler flow that does not interact with the Deployment Tools can be used in the case that the VRE is already available for the user:

1. The Dispatcher receives a request from the Matchmaker to run an analysis with a Package for Processing Datasets. The Dispatcher will activate the adequate plugins for the Compute Engine and Data Access Layer, according to the specification.
2. Because the VRE is not yet instantiated, the Compute Engine requests the deployment of a new instance of the VRE to the Deployment Tools.
3. The Deployment Tools perform the necessary actions on the infrastructure to deploy the VRE instance and eventually return a ready-to-use VRE endpoint to the Compute Engine.
4. Both the Compute Engine and Data Access Layer prepare the target VRE for performing the analytics (e.g. transferring data if needed).
5. When ready, the dispatcher returns a URL to the EOSC Matchmaker for the user to interact with the deployed analysis.
6. Once the analysis is finalised, the Compute Engine will clean up resources on the Compute Platform through the Deployment Tools. The Data Access Layer may further perform operations to make data available for the user, e.g. storing it to a temporary staging server where it can be downloaded, keeping it in a persistent space within the Compute Platform, or other options that will be refined with the help of the use cases.

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Figure 6 - EOSC Data Player runtime flow.

6. EOSC interoperability

EOSC Data Commons services are designed to operate in the EOSC environment and follow relevant EOSC Interoperability Framework (IF) guidelines and integrate with the EOSC Core Capabilities. This is demonstrated by the different technology choices and project initiatives detailed below.

The EOSC Matchmaker Metadata Crawlers are designed to interoperate with diverse repository technologies and metadata schemas, enabling a wide range of compatibility with available repositories. The first target of the crawlers is OAI-PMH with DataCite 4.6, following the EOSC IF for Research Products (EOSC IF metadata schema entirely inspired by DataCite.org, with extensions required to model links to funders and grants). Similarly, the EOSC Matchmaker will offer an OAI-PMH endpoint to support harvesting from other Nodes.

The EOSC Player has EOSC EU Node as one of the targets for executing the users analysis by submitting workloads to the available compute services:

- The Deployment Tools of EOSC Player can deploy the needed services and tools on the Managed Compute (VMs) and Managed Containers services of EOSC EU Node, as Infrastructure Manager already supports OpenStack and Kubernetes interfaces to create virtual infrastructures.
- The Compute Engines of EOSC Data Player supports the Managed Notebooks service with its JupyterHub plugin, so it can deploy the user's Notebooks on the EOSC EU Node.
- The Data Access Layer includes a plugin for the ScienceMesh, thus allowing data available in the EOSC EU Node File Sync & Share service to be accessible for processing by EOSC Data Commons. This feature was already demonstrated as part of the launch of the EOSC Federation³ in the integration of the CERN Node with the EU Node.

The *Package for Processing Datasets* will be proposed as a new guideline in the EOSC Interoperability Framework, allowing for the federated setup of the EOSC Data Commons services, with the Matchmaker hosted in one EOSC Node, interacting with a Data Player service instance hosted in another node, thus bringing new ways of interlinking different EOSC Nodes. The Package can be used as well as a general reproducible and interoperable way of sharing analysis between researchers and its adoption. This package is in line with the [Technical interoperability in the EOSC Federation and initial gap analysis](#) recommendation for establishing a minimum set of rules describing digital assets and codifying their technical conformity (Section 4.1 of the document, Data and metadata interoperability through radical transparency).

Table 20 summarizes the main integration points to be developed between the EOSC Core Capabilities and EOSC Data Commons.

³ See Introducing the EOSC Federation session at EOSC Symposium 2025 , slides available at [link](#)

Core capability	EOSC Data Commons integration
Resource Catalogue and Registry Services	OAI-PMH as first metadata crawler implementation, aiming at maximising the number of compatible repositories with the Matchmaker and facilitating the ingestion of metadata from existing repositories. OAI-PMH interface implemented for interoperability with other EOSC Nodes.
AAI	EOSC Data Player interacts with the compute infrastructure relying on the EOSC AAI federated credentials and the AARC Blueprint Architecture using OpenID Connect.
Service and Research Product Accounting	EOSC Data Commons will provide comprehensive information on the usage, including (but not limited to): number of harvested repositories, number of datasets, number of tools available in the tool catalogue, number of searches performed by users, number of linked tools with datasets, number of Packages for processing datasets produced, number of FAIR Assessments performed, and number of analysis deployed. These metrics will be made available for its ingestion into the EOSC Accounting service of the EOSC Nodes delivering the services.
Service Monitoring	The EOSC Data Commons Services will include probes for checking the correct function of the services. These probes will be developed following the EOSC Service Monitoring specifications
Application Workflow Management	Similarly to the EOSC Data Player, the Application Workflow Management (AWM) supports the deployment of Tools into EOSC Compute infrastructure with Tools defined as TOSCA Templates. The EOSC Data Player with IM as a central component can easily support TOSCA templates and bring compatibility with the AWM. As the AWM API will be further defined, AWM can be one of the plugins implemented for the Compute Engines.

Table 20 - EOSC Core capabilities and EOSC Data Commons

7. Conclusions and Future Work

This deliverable provides the initial functional specification and architectural blueprint for the EOSC Data Commons Services. It provides the design principles, requirements, architectural decisions, and component descriptions that will support the first integrated release of the EOSC Matchmaker and the EOSC Data Player. The architecture presented here establishes an extensible basis for enabling AI-powered data discovery, tool-dataset pairing, provenance-aware packaging, and orchestrated execution of analysis workflows across the compute continuum.

The architecture will evolve iteratively as technical development progresses and as real-world use cases continue to refine functional and interoperability requirements. The upcoming release— D3.2 (initial services, June 2026) and the corresponding use case demonstrations— will provide essential feedback for validating design assumptions, identifying gaps, and prioritising enhancements. Moreover, the evolution of the EOSC Federation, launched in November 2025, will introduce new operational contexts, policies, and capabilities that the architecture will need to incorporate.

Deliverable D3.3, scheduled for March 2027, will provide a comprehensive update of the architecture, integrating lessons learned from the Proof of Concept evaluation (November 2025), subsequent deployments and refined requirements emerging from D7.2 and D7.3. Future work will focus on strengthening cross-node interoperability, expanding the plugin ecosystems for metadata ingestion and compute engines, refining semantic search capabilities, and enhancing reproducibility and portability of analysis packages. These developments will progressively reinforce the EOSC Data Commons as a solid foundation for building EOSC as the federated European Research Commons.

Acronyms

Acronym	Definition
AAI	Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure
AARC	Authentication and Authorisation for Research and Collaboration
ADR	Architecture Decision Record
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AI-MWDS	AI-based Analytics Oriented Metadata Warehouse and Discovery Service
API	Application Programming Interface
AWM	Application Workflow Management
AWS	Amazon Web Services
CNCF	Cloud Native Computing Foundation
DAODS	Data Analysis Orchestration and Deployment Service
HPC	High Performance Computing
HTC	High Throughput Computing
IaaS	Infrastructure as a Service
IF	Interoperability Framework
IM	Infrastructure Manager
LLM	Large Language Model
MIME	Multipurpose Internet Mail Extensions
MCP	Model Context Protocol
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
PID	Persistent Identifier
TCB	Technical Coordination Board
TOSCA	Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications
UI	User Interface
VM	Virtual Machine
VMI	Virtual Machine Image
VRE	Virtual Research Environment